

Oxidation of some vicinal and non-vicinal diols by tetrakis(pyridine)silver dichromate : A kinetic and mechanistic study

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Abstract : The kinetics of oxidation of four vicinal, four non-vicinal diols and two of their monoethers by tetrakis(pyridine)-silver dichromate (TPSD) have been studied in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO). The main product of oxidation is the corresponding hydroxycarbonyl compound. The reaction is first order in TPSD. Michaelis-Menten type of kinetics is observed with respect to the diols. The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions. The hydrogen ion dependence has the form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b [\text{H}^+]$. The oxidation of [1,1,2,2-²H₄] ethanediol exhibits a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}} = 5.91$ at 298 K). The reaction has been studied in nineteen different organic solvents and the solvent effect has been analysed using Taft's and Swain's multiparametric equations. The temperature dependence of the kinetic isotope effect indicates the presence of a symmetrical transition state in the rate-determining step. A suitable mechanism has been proposed.

Keywords : Correlation analysis, dichromate, diols, kinetics, mechanism, oxidation.

Introduction

Inorganic salts of Cr^{VI} are well known oxidants for the organic compounds. However these salts are rather drastic and non-selective oxidants. Further, they are insoluble in most organic solvents. Thus miscibility is a problem. To overcome these limitations, a large number of organic derivatives of Cr^{VI} have been prepared and used in organic synthesis as mild and selective oxidants in non-aqueous solvents¹. One of such compounds is tetrakis(pyridine)silver dichromate (TPSD), reported by Firozabadi *et al.*². We have been interested in the kinetic and mechanistic aspects of the oxidation by complex salts of Cr^{VI} and several reports on halochromates have already reported from our laboratory³⁻⁶. There seems to be no report on the oxidation aspects of diols using tetrakis(pyridine)silver dichromate (TPSD). Therefore, it was of interest to investigate the kinetics of the oxidation of some vicinal and non-vicinal diols by TPSD in DMSO. A suitable mechanism has also been postulated.

Results and discussion

Stoichiometry : The homogeneity of the DNP derivatives indicated the formation of only one product in each case. Under our reaction conditions, therefore, there is no observable oxidation of the second hydroxy group. This may be due to the presence of a large excess of the diol over TPSD. The overall reaction may, therefore, be written as eq. (1).

Kinetic dependence : The reactions are of first order with respect to TPSD. Further, the pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} is independent of the initial concentration of TPSD. Fig. 1 depict a typical kinetic run. The reaction rate increases with increase in the concentration of the diols but not linearly (Table 1). A plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ against $1/[\text{Diol}]$ is linear ($r > 0.995$) with an intercept on the rate-ordinate (Fig. 2). Thus, Michaelis-Menten type

[†]In Commemoration of the 150th Birth Anniversary of Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray.

Fig. 1. Oxidation of ethane-diol by TPSD at 308 K : A typical kinetic run.

Fig. 2. $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{Diol}]$: A double reciprocal plot.

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of propan-1,2-diol by TPSD at 308 K

10^3 [TPSD] (mol dm ⁻³)	[Diol] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)
1.0	0.10	4.47
1.0	0.20	6.82
1.0	0.40	9.26
1.0	0.60	10.5
1.0	0.80	11.3
1.0	1.00	11.8
1.0	1.50	12.5
1.0	3.00	13.4
2.0	0.40	10.2
4.0	0.40	9.36
6.0	0.40	10.4
8.0	0.40	9.54
1.0	0.20	7.02 ^a

^aContained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

kinetics are observed with respect to the diol. This leads to the postulation of following overall mechanism (2) and (3) and rate law (4).

$$\text{Rate} = k_2 K [\text{Diol}] [\text{TPSD}] / (1 + K [\text{Diol}]) \quad (4)$$

The dependence of reaction rate on the reductant concentration was studied at different temperatures and the values of K and k_2 were evaluated from the double reciprocal plots. The thermodynamic parameters of the complex formation and activation parameters of the decomposition of the complexes were calculated from the values of K and k_2 respectively at different temperatures (Tables 2 and 3).

Test for free radicals : The oxidation of diols, by TPSD, in an atmosphere of nitrogen failed to induce the polymerisation of acrylonitrile. Further, addition of acry-

Table 2. Rate constants for the decomposition of TPSD-diol complexes and activation parameters

Diols	$10^4 k_2$ (s ⁻¹)				ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S^*$ (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
Ethane-1,2-diol	2.34	5.94	14.4	35.1	66.0 ± 0.6	86 ± 2	91.4 ± 0.5
Propane-1,2-diol	9.54	21.6	50.4	108	59.3 ± 0.6	97 ± 2	88.2 ± 0.5
Butane-2,3-diol	39.6	83.7	171	351	52.7 ± 0.5	108 ± 2	84.8 ± 0.4
Butane-1,2-diol	12.6	27.0	64.8	135	58.1 ± 1.0	99 ± 3	87.5 ± 0.8
Propane-1,3-diol	18.0	40.5	90.0	198	58.3 ± 0.7	96 ± 2	86.6 ± 0.5
Butane-1,3-diol	22.5	46.8	99.0	207	53.8 ± 0.8	109 ± 3	86.2 ± 0.6
Butane-1,4-diol	26.1	56.7	126	270	56.9 ± 0.7	97 ± 2	85.8 ± 0.6
Pantane-1,5-diol	36.0	76.5	154	324	52.9 ± 0.8	108 ± 2	85.1 ± 0.6
3-Methoxy-butan-1-ol	44.1	93.6	189	405	53.4 ± 0.9	105 ± 3	84.6 ± 0.7
DED ^a	0.38	1.03	2.62	6.72	70.2 ± 0.6	86 ± 2	95.7 ± 0.5
k_H/k_D	6.12	5.77	5.50	5.22			

^a[1,1,2,2-²H₄]Ethane-1,2-diol.

Table 3. Formation constants for the decomposition of TPSD-diols complexes and thermodynamic parameters

Diols	K (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)				$-\Delta H$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S$ (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	$-\Delta G$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
Ethane-1,2-diol	5.76	5.15	4.50	3.96	12.1 ± 0.3	19 ± 1	6.53 ± 0.2
Propane-1,2-diol	6.95	6.35	5.69	5.04	10.7 ± 0.4	13 ± 1	7.04 ± 0.3
Butane-2,3-diol	5.13	4.50	3.81	3.24	14.2 ± 0.4	28 ± 1	6.18 ± 0.3
Butane-1,2-diol	6.93	6.31	5.70	5.08	10.3 ± 0.3	12 ± 1	7.04 ± 0.2
Propane-1,3-diol	6.48	5.90	5.22	4.60	11.2 ± 0.4	15 ± 1	6.86 ± 0.3
Butane-1,3-diol	5.49	4.90	4.28	3.63	13.0 ± 0.5	23 ± 2	6.39 ± 0.4
Butane-1,4-diol	6.84	6.20	5.61	4.95	10.6 ± 0.3	13 ± 1	7.00 ± 0.3
Pantane-1,5-diol	5.85	5.25	4.55	3.92	12.7 ± 0.5	21 ± 2	6.56 ± 0.4
3-Methoxy-butan-1-ol	6.66	6.05	5.40	4.75	11.1 ± 0.4	14 ± 1	6.93 ± 0.3
DED ^a	6.57	5.91	5.35	4.68	10.9 ± 0.4	14 ± 1	6.89 ± 0.3

Table 4. Dependence of the reaction rate on hydrogen-ion concentration

[Ethane-1,2-diol] = 0.10 mol dm⁻³; [TPSD] = 0.001 mol dm⁻³; Temp. = 308 K

[TsOH] (mol dm ⁻³)	0.10	0.20	0.40	0.60	0.80	1.00
10 ⁴ k_{obs} (s ⁻¹)	5.31	6.21	7.74	9.45	11.7	12.6

lonitrile had no effect on the rate (Table 1). To further confirm the absence of free radicals in the reaction pathway, the reaction was carried out in the presence of 0.05 mol dm⁻³ of 2,6-di-*t*-butyl-4-methylphenol (butylated hydroxytoluene or BHT). It was observed that BHT was recovered unchanged, almost quantitatively.

Effect of hydrogen ions : The reaction is catalyzed by hydrogen ions (Table 4). The hydrogen-ion dependence has the form : $k_{obs} = a + b [H^+]$. The values of a and b for ethanediol are $4.49 \pm 0.23 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $8.40 \pm 0.38 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively ($r^2 = 0.9920$).

Kinetic isotope effect : To ascertain the importance of the cleavage of the α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step, the oxidation of DED was studied. Results (Tables 2 and 3) showed the formation constants, K , of the intermediate complex of the deuteriated and protiated diols do not differ much, however, the rate of disproportionation of the intermediate exhibited the presence of a substantial primary kinetic isotope ($k_H/k_D = 5.91$ at 298 K).

Effect of organic solvents : The oxidation of ethanediol was studied in 19 different organic solvents. The choice of solvents was limited due to the solubility of TPSD and its reaction with primary and secondary alcohols. There was no reaction with the solvents chosen. The values of formation constants K and decomposition constants of the complex, k_2 are recorded in Table 5.

A satisfactory linear correlation ($r^2 = 0.9064$) between the values of activation enthalpies and entropies of

Table 5. Effect of solvents on the oxidation of ethane-1,2-diol by TPSD at 308 K

Solvents	K (dm ⁻³ mol ⁻¹)	10 ⁵ k_2 (s ⁻¹)	Solvents	K (dm ⁻³ mol ⁻¹)	10 ⁵ k_2 (s ⁻¹)
Chloroform	5.92	41.7	Toluene	5.13	18.2
1,2-Dichloroethane	4.68	51.3	Acetophenone	6.12	77.6
Dichloromethane	4.45	49.0	THF	4.57	31.6
DMSO	4.50	144	<i>t</i> -Butylalcohol	4.83	19.9
Acetone	5.62	57.5	1,4-Dioxane	4.72	27.5
DMF	4.65	95.4	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	5.14	14.8
Butanone	5.44	34.7	CS ₂	4.89	9.77
Nitrobenzene	4.13	63.1	Acetic acid	5.49	8.32
Benzene	6.31	22.4	Ethyl acetate	5.14	24.5
Cyclohexane	5.41	2.82			

Fig. 3. Exner's isokinetic relationship in the oxidation of diols by TPSD.

oxidation of diols indicated the operation of compensation effect in this reaction⁷. The reaction also exhibited an excellent isokinetic effect, as determined by Exner's criterion⁸. An Exner's plot between $\log k_2$ at 288 K and at 318 K was linear ($r^2 = 0.9984$) (Fig. 3). The value of isokinetic temperature is 788 ± 108 K. The linear isokinetic correlation implies that all the diols are oxidized by the same mechanism and the changes in rate are governed by the changes in both the enthalpy and entropy of the activation.

Solvent effect: The rate constants, k_2 , for the oxidation of ethanediol in 18 organic solvents (CS_2 was not considered, as the complete range of solvent parameters was not available) did not exhibit any significant correlation in terms of the linear solvation energy relationship (5) of Kamlet *et al.*⁹.

$$\log k_2 = A_0 + p\pi^* + b\beta + a\alpha \quad (5)$$

In this equation, π^* represents the solvent polarity, β the hydrogen bond acceptor basicities and α is the hydrogen bond donor acidity. A_0 is the intercept term. It may be mentioned here that out of the 18 solvents, 13 have a value of zero for α . The results of correlation analyses in terms of eq. (5), a biparametric equation involving π^* and β , and separately with π^* and β are given below eqs. (6)–(9).

$$\log k_2 = -4.54 + (1.40 \pm 0.18)\pi^* + (0.22 \pm 0.15)\beta - (0.26 \pm 0.14)\alpha \quad (6)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8659; sd = 0.16; n = 18; \Psi = 0.40$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.47 + (1.49 \pm 0.18)\pi^* + (0.14 \pm 0.15)\beta \quad (7)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8327; sd = 0.17; n = 18; \Psi = 0.43$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.50 + (1.53 \pm 0.18)\pi^* \quad (8)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8236; sd = 0.17; n = 18; \Psi = 0.43$$

$$\log k_2 = -3.66 + (0.40 \pm 0.33)\beta \quad (9)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0848; sd = 0.40; n = 18; \Psi = 0.98$$

Here n is the number of data points and Ψ is the Exner's statistical parameter¹⁰.

Kamlet's⁹ triparametric equation explains *ca.* 86% of the effect of solvent on the oxidation. However, by Exner's criterion¹⁰ the correlation is not even satisfactory (*cf.* eq. 6). The major contribution is of solvent polarity. It alone accounted for *ca.* 82% of the data. Both β and α play relatively minor roles.

The data on the solvent effect were analysed in terms of Swain's¹¹ eq. (10) of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents also.

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (10)$$

Here A represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent and B the cation-solvating power. C is the intercept term. $(A + B)$ is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analysed in terms of eq. (11), separately with A and B and with $(A + B)$.

$$\log k_2 = (0.37 \pm 0.05)A + (1.57 \pm 0.03)B - 3.65 \quad (11)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9930; sd = 0.04; n = 19; \Psi = 0.09$$

$$\log k_2 = 0.15 (\pm 0.52)A - 2.57 \quad (12)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0048; sd = 0.42; n = 19; \Psi = 1.02$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.54 (\pm 0.07)B - 3.53 \quad (13)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9633; sd = 0.08; n = 19; \Psi = 0.20$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.17 \pm 0.16(A + B) - 3.61 \quad (14)$$

$$r^2 = 0.7698; sd = 0.20; n = 19; \Psi = 0.49$$

The rates of oxidation of ethanediol in different solvents showed an excellent correlation in Swain's equation (*cf.* eq. 11) with the cation-solvating power playing the major role. In fact, the cation-solvation alone account for *ca.* 96% of the data. The correlation with the anion-solvating power was very poor. The solvent polarity, represented

by ($A + B$), also accounted for *ca.* 77% of the data. In view of the fact that solvent polarity is able to account for *ca.* 77% of the data, an attempt was made to correlate the rate with the relative permittivity of the solvent. However, a plot of $\log k_2$ against the inverse of the relative permittivity is not linear ($r^2 = 0.5345$; $sd = 0.29$; $\psi = 0.70$).

Correlation analysis of reactivity :

The rates of oxidation of the four vicinal diols in DMSO showed the excellent correlation with Taft's σ^* values¹² with negative reaction constants (Table 6), this indicates the presence of an electron-deficient rate-determining step.

Table 6. Reaction constants of the oxidation of vicinal diols by TPSD

T (K)	ρ^*	R^2	sd	ψ
288	-1.25 ± 0.09	0.9890	0.06	0.12
298	-1.17 ± 0.07	0.9933	0.05	0.09
308	-1.10 ± 0.09	0.9865	0.06	0.13
318	-1.02 ± 0.07	0.9906	0.05	0.11

Here $\Sigma \sigma^*$ represents the sum of the substituent constants for the substituents present on the two alcoholic carbons of the vicinal diols. The fact that σ^* values alone able to account for 99% of the data showed that steric factors do not play any significant role in the reaction. The magnitude of the reaction constants decreases with an increase in the temperature, indicating that selectivity decreases with an increase in the reactivity.

Mechanism :

The presence of a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect confirms the cleavage of an α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step. The negative values of the polar reaction constant together with substantial deuterium isotope effect indicate that the transition state has an electron-deficient carbon centre. Hence the transfer of a hydride-ion from diol to the oxidant is suggested. The hydride-transfer mechanism is also supported by the major role of cation-solvating power of solvents.

The hydride ion transfer may take place either by a cyclic process via an ester intermediate or by an acyclic one-step bimolecular process. Kwart and Nickle¹³ have shown that a study of the dependence of the kinetic isotope effect on temperature can be gainfully employed to

resolve this problem. The data for protio- and deuterio-ethandiols, fitted to the familiar expression $k_H/k_D = A_H/A_D \exp(E_a/RT)$ ^{14,15} show a direct correspondence with the properties of a symmetrical transition state in which the activation energy difference (ΔE_a) for k_H/k_D is equal to the zero-point energy difference for the respective C-H and C-D bonds (≈ 4.5 kJ/mol) and the frequency factors and the entropies of activation of the respective reactions are nearly equal. Bordwell¹⁶ has documented a very cogent evidence against the occurrence of concerted one-step bimolecular processes by hydrogen transfer and it is evident that in the present studies also the hydrogen transfer does not occur by an acyclic bimolecular process. It is well established that intrinsically concerted sigmatropic reactions, characterized by transfer of hydrogen in a cyclic transition state, are the only truly symmetrical processes involving a linear hydrogen transfer¹⁷. Littler¹⁸ has also shown that a cyclic hydride transfer, in the oxidation of alcohols by Cr^{VI} , involves six electrons and, being a Huckel-type system, is an allowed process. Thus the overall mechanism is proposed to involve the formation of a chromate ester in a fast pre-equilibrium step and then a disproportionation of the ester in a subsequent slow step via a cyclic concerted symmetrical transition state leading to the product (Scheme 1). The observed hydrogen-ion dependence can be explained by assuming a rapid reversible protonation of the chromate ester (A) with the protonated ester decomposing at a rate faster than (A) (Scheme 2).

It is of interest to recall that pinacol is oxidized by chromic acid but not by TPSD. Chatterjee and Mukherji¹⁹ reported an abrupt change from butane-2,3-diol to pinacol, the latter reacting very fast. As pointed out by Littler¹⁸, a cyclic ester mechanism is forbidden in the diol- Cr^{VI} reaction. Chromic acid oxidation of pinacol may therefore involve two one-electron steps. Chromic acid oxidations are known to induce polymerization of acrylamide under certain conditions²⁰. No such observation has yet been recorded with TPSD. Thus the capability of chromic acid and the inability of TPSD to act as a one-electron oxidant may explain the different behaviour of pinacol towards these two oxidants.

Scheme 1. Acid-independent path.

Scheme 2. Acid-dependent path.

Experimental

Materials : The diols and the monoethers (BDH or Fluka) were distilled under reduced pressure before use. TPSD was prepared by the reported method². [1,1,2,2-²H₄]Ethane-1,2-diol (DED) was prepared by reducing diethyl oxalate with lithium aluminium deuteride²¹. Its isotopic purity, determined by its NMR spectrum, was 95 ± 3%. Due to the non-aqueous nature of the medium, toluene-*p*-sulphonic acid (TsOH) was used as a source of hydrogen ions. TsOH is a strong acid and in a polar solvent like DMSO, it is likely to be completely ionized.

Product analysis : Product analysis was carried out

under kinetic conditions. In a typical experiment, ethane-1,2-diol (0.1 mol) and TPSD (0.01 mol) were taken in DMSO (100 ml) and the mixture was allowed to stand in the dark for *ca.* 10 h to ensure completion of the reaction. Most of the solvent was removed under reduced pressure and residue treated overnight with an excess (250 ml) of a saturated solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in 2 mol dm⁻³ HCl. The precipitated 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (DNP) was filtered off, dried, recrystallized from ethanol and weighed. The product was found identical (m.p. and mixed m.p.) with an authentic sample of DNP of hydroxyethanol.

Kinetic measurements : The reactions were followed under pseudo-first order conditions keeping a large excess ($\times 15$ or greater) of the diols over TPSD. The temperature was kept constant to ± 0.1 K. The solvent was DMSO, unless specified otherwise. The reactions were followed by monitoring the decrease in the concentration of TPSD spectrophotometrically at 365 nm for up to 80% of the reaction. No other reactant or product has any significant absorption at this wave-length. The pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} , were evaluated from the linear ($r = 0.995-0.999$) plots of $\log [\text{TPSD}]$ against time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 4\%$. All experiments, other than those for studying the effect of hydrogen ions, were carried out in the absence of TsOH.

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